

humantech solutions:

Smarter. Safer. Greener.

Shaping the future of construction with innovative, human-centred technologies for a safer, smarter, and more sustainable industry.

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The HumanTech project is helping shape the future of construction by putting people at the centre of digital transformation.

Over three years, we have brought together robotics, artificial intelligence, wearable systems, and other digital tools combining the diverse expertise of our 21 partners. The result? **A set of technologies designed to improve safety, boost efficiency, and support more sustainable building practices** at every stage of the construction process.

Our HumanTech technologies cover a wide range of applications. From autonomous robotic systems and wearable support for physically demanding tasks, to dynamic digital twins, smart bridge inspections, and AI-powered defect detection.

These solutions are the result of close **collaboration between researchers, technology providers, industry leaders, and end users**, ensuring they are not only innovative, but also practical, adaptable, and ready to be used in real construction environments — helping teams avoid delays, reduce physical strain, monitor progress, take better decisions on site and remotely and improve working conditions while increasing productivity.

In this brochure, you will find some of HumanTech's most impactful outcomes and learn how we are contributing to make construction smarter, safer, and greener, with humans at the centre.

Find out more at humantech-horizon.eu

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BIMxD Software

Partners involved

CATENDA, HC, TUK, UPD

Reference deliverables and useful material

D1.4 HT architecture definitions (final)

D2.1 BIMxD IDM with classes and attributes according to ISO 29481 and respective standards

D2.2 Open source BIM authoring tools: Framework and Software Modules This includes a set of open source tools to do BIM authoring related tasks

D2.3 BIMxD platform

Included in D2.3 is the software that was behind the running online web/api server in HumanTech – it supports tools related to BIM and point clouds models and interactive visualization of these

D2.4 bSDD specification from BIMxD

D2.5 IFC schema extension

Description of the technology

BIMxD” is an extended Building Information Modeling formulation designed to capture all structural and semantic dimensions relevant to activity on construction sites. BIMxD underpins a new type of Dynamic Semantic Digital Twin (DSDT) for construction environments. This DSDT is used to continuously collect data—such as geometric details, material composition, or worker positioning—and updates the model in real time, thus creating a comprehensive, semantically rich digital representation of the site.

The intention is for BIMxD to serve as a single shared reference for everyone involved in the build—engineers, on-site crews using wearable devices or exoskeletons, and autonomous robots navigating and collecting data. By fusing diverse data sources into one integrated model, BIMxD goes beyond the usual 3D or 4D BIM approaches, adding multiple “dimensions” (for instance, safety, resource use, and semantic labeling) that capture the evolving state of a construction site in far greater detail. This helps coordinate human tasks, improves safety and efficiency, and supports greener, more resource-conscious construction practices.

In practical terms, BIMxD consists of three main parts

1. The HumanTech server. It is running on Ubuntu Linux. The API-server and web-server is using FastAPI and the Python programming language. It uses Huew for long running tasks. It has support for importing BIM and point cloud files – and interactive visualization of them, scheduling (it can import MS Project files), BCF tasks, Construction site position markers and other things supporting the Digital Twin flow.
2. A set of tools has been created for authoring/editing BIM/IFC files. This includes tools for converting an interactive click on surface (wall) in 3D BIM viewer into getting which wall was interacted with and handing that over to the robot task planner. This was shown in one of the pilots. It also

includes tools to convert identifies objects in a point cloud into geometries in IFC format.

3. BIMxD also consists of the concepts/relations created in D2.4 and D2.5 - bsDD specification and IFC extension. In practice, several of the extensions has been made using bsDD – which is seen as a dynamic (but standardized) way of adding properties to IFC.

Benefits for stakeholders / impact of the technology

Using BIMxD a stakeholder can plan and keep track of a construction project in an innovative way.

The digital twin makes it possible to create and follow up a schedule that is related to BIM-models and then use scans of construction with a certain interval to estimate the progress and if it is according to plan.

It allows managing BIM and point cloud data and construction site marker positions. It also has support for connections with robot planning and remote instructions for robot tasks (via the robot ontology system in HumanTech).

Image above BIMxD web interface used for giving remote instructions to the demolition robot from Kajima (physically in Singapore) to the pilot site in Madrid

Image above BIM/IFC model revisions stored in the BIMxD system

Image above Schedule task from construction project related to BIM objects (photovoltaic cells)

360-degree Time-of-Flight camera

Partners involved

RICOH, DFKI, RPTU, IMPLENIA, ZHAW

Reference deliverables and useful material

D3.2 360-degree Time-of-flight RGB+depth camera prototype

D7.1 Digital Twin for material optimization and safety monitoring

Description of the technology

Ricoh introduce an innovative, portable, omnidirectional RGB-D scanner with a 5-meter range in all directions. This scanner is composed of two fisheye RGB cameras, two types of Time-of-Flight (ToF) light emitters, and a ToF detector with a four-lens configuration. A built-in microcomputer enables exposure adjustments, data verification, and shooting control via Wi-Fi from a smartphone or PC.

Captured RGB and depth images are transmitted to a PC, where they are aligned and converted into a 3D point cloud. By capturing images at 2 to 3-meter intervals, individual 3D datasets can be aligned to cover large areas seamlessly. Additionally, using the AR markers introduced in D3.1, users can register accurate scan positions within a BIM model. What sets this scanner apart from conventional 3D sensing devices is its field of view and scanning speed.

Traditional terrestrial scanners require tens of seconds to complete a scan. While compact 3D scanners can capture at high speeds—at tens of frames per second (fps)—they must sequentially scan an entire scene, which is labor-intensive and prone to cumulative measurement errors, making them unsuitable for large-scale environments. In contrast, our proposed scanner captures a full 360-degree field of view in just one second.

Ensuring stable measurements in challenging environments, such as construction sites, is critical. ToF scanning is particularly vulnerable to accuracy degradation due to strong ambient light—such as in outdoor environments—or Multi-Path Interference (MPI) in confined spaces.

To address these challenges, we have developed advanced AI-based noise reduction techniques for ambient light interference and proprietary ToF components that mitigate the effects of MPI. These innovations allow users to effortlessly capture on-site data and continuously monitor construction progress against BIM models, enabling efficient project management and informed decision-making.

Benefits for stakeholders / impact of the technology

For Construction Teams & Site Workers

- **Labor-Saving 3D Scanning:** With significantly improved scanning efficiency per unit area, scanning time is drastically reduced.
- **Flexible Shooting Process:** Each scan takes just one second, eliminating concerns about movement of people or objects at the site.

For Project Managers & Coordinators

- **Better Progress Tracking:** The ease of 3D scanning enables more frequent data collection, enhancing the accuracy of progress monitoring.
- **Flexible Shooting Process:** Each scan takes just one second, eliminating concerns about movement of people or objects at the site.

For Owners & Clients

- **Better Documentation:** Viewing aligned 3D data with images allows for easy distance measurement and quality checks directly on the images.
- **Informed Decision-Making:** Real-time construction insights ensure that investments remain aligned with project objectives.

15.08.2024

18.09.2024

16.10.2024

22.11.2024

Scan-to-BIM Pipeline

Partners involved

DFKI, RPTU, RICOH

Reference deliverables and useful material

D3.6 Complete Scan-to-BIMxD Digital Twin pipeline

Description of the technology

The HumanTech project has delivered several results that support scan-to-BIM workflows including models for semantic segmentation of point clouds, geometric reconstruction algorithms and open BIM authoring tools. All these tools can be combined into a comprehensive scan-to-BIM pipeline. The award-winning HumanTech pipeline has been intensively tested on datasets with various features, mainly reconstructing multi-storey office, hospital or residential buildings.

The semantic segmentation models employ state-of-the-art architectures. For training, publicly available datasets were used along with data scanned and annotated in the HumanTech project. The resulting models reach state-of-the-art segmentation accuracy yet augmenting the available models by

more classes. To support the pilot implementation, a specific focus has been set to support the segmentation of construction specific classes including construction support, scaffolding, formwork, etc.

For training the semantic segmentation models for the construction domain, HumanTech developed a specialized annotation guideline for joint image-point cloud annotation. The guideline is the first of its kind combining both modalities and covering the construction field ontology with the goal of advancing the deep learning field for the construction industry by creating a standard for data annotation.

The geometric reconstruction algorithms have been delivered based on state-of-the-art method mainly supporting reconstruction of building scenes. The algorithms are available in an open-source python package supporting further research and development activities.

To support open data exchange, the reconstructed objects have to be presented in an open format. In HumanTech, IFC was the format of choice. To create IFC objects from the previously reconstructed objects, the openbimxd python package was created and released. Beyond the creation of IFC objects, openbimxd supports other processes including filtering, parsing and semantic label transfer.

HumanTech developments in the Scan-to-BIM field are not only a leap forward in technology capabilities, but also a significant contribution to the scientific literature and tools relating to the field. The results achieved in HumanTech lay the groundwork for future research and commercial applications.

Head-mounted wide-angle camera

Partners involved

RICOH, SCI-TRACK

Reference deliverables and useful material

D4.1 Body sensor network with integrated camera approach

Description of the technology

This new wearable camera is developed to achieve three essential goals: compactness that minimizes interference with the user, synchronization with external devices to address localization drift caused by magnetic interference affecting IMUs, and a wide field of view that captures both the user's body and their environment simultaneously.

Conventional fisheye-integrated cameras generally fall into two categories. Consumer models are lightweight and easy to use but lack advanced features such as hardware triggering and low-latency image transmission, which are critical for time-synchronized hardware systems. On the other hand, industrial or developer-focused models are rich in functionality but tend to be

large and uncomfortable to wear. Bridging this gap, Sci-Track and RICOH have jointly developed a new camera that combines the advantages of both types in a form factor suitable for wearable use.

The camera features two fisheye optical units facing opposite directions, providing a field of view greater than 180 degrees to fully capture the spatial environment. Each lens is paired with an image sensor, offering a resolution of 2592 by 2048 pixels and supporting a maximum frame rate of 73 frames per second with a global shutter.

The sensor system supports three acquisition modes: free-run, software-triggered, and hardware-triggered. The hardware trigger uses a 5V GPIO input and provides microsecond-order latency, which is negligible relative to IMU sampling rates.

A wide range of image acquisition parameters—including frame rate, exposure time, brightness, and digital gain—can be configured, offering flexibility for varied environments such as construction sites or industrial settings. Thanks to an innovative optical design involving multiple internal reflections, the camera's optical components are significantly more compact compared to conventional 1-inch fisheye lenses.

The sensors and optics are integrated into a single aluminum housing that is both lightweight and highly thermally conductive, with anodizing on the surface for durability. For mounting, the camera is designed to be compatible with both the HoloLens 2 and Trimble XR10, using custom brackets and screws. Two mounting positions—central and side—are available, allowing users to select the appropriate configuration depending on use-case and balance. In both setups, the front-facing lens captures the user's movements while the rear-facing lens records the surrounding environment, facilitating re-localization of the user with respect to building and its BIM model.

Benefits for stakeholders /impact of the technology

For hardware system integrator

- Synchronized video/image streaming with other system in various types of image format such as fisheye, equirectangular and perspective
- Compact housing design for large 1 inch dual image sensors

For software developer

- Fully controllable image acquisition settings with SDK
- Compatibility to platform such as ROS

Intelligent Exoskeleton with intention prediction

Partners involved

TECNALIA, SCI-TRACK

Reference deliverables and useful material

D4.1 Body sensor network with integrated camera approach

D4.2 Intelligent exoskeleton with intention prediction prototype

Exoskeleton pilot and tests

D7.2 Human-Robot collaboration and wearables

D6.4 HT worker assessment report

Description of the technology

Workers in the construction industry are known to have increased rates of work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) with the back and shoulders being the most affected body regions.

While there are many different intervention approaches to control WMSDs in construction several construction tasks remain physically demanding, in-

volve frequent exposure to known WMSD risk factors, and can be challenging to redesign or eliminate.

One potential tool to prevent WMSDs in construction is the use of exoskeletons. Exoskeletons can be defined as personal assistance systems that affect the body mechanically, helping its musculoskeletal system to perform a certain task or movement. Exoskeletons specifically designed to alleviate muscular stress in workers are referred to as occupational exoskeletons (OEs). Depending on how they generate assistance, OEs can be categorized as either active or passive. Active exoskeletons have electric, hydraulic, and pneumatic actuators while passive ones have springs and elastic elements that harvest energy in one movement and release it in another.

Regardless of whether they are active or passive, current exoskeletons require direct interaction from the user to activate mechanisms or adjust assistance levels. This approach works well when the tasks are not very dynamic, and the user spend most of the time in a certain posture. However, when the movements are very different and dynamic, manually controlling the device can become impractical and cumbersome.

As part of the Humantech project, an innovative prototype of an advanced upper-limb exoskeleton has been developed. What makes this exoskeleton unique is its ability to activate based on the user's intent, which is inferred from their kinematics using data from a Body Sensor Network (BSN). The main objective is to leverage the exoskeleton to reduce physical strain, minimizing the effort required by the worker while offering a more intuitive and less intrusive user experience. By simplifying its operation, the system also reduces the mental effort needed to control the exoskeleton, making it a seamless extension of the worker's natural movements.

Traditional inertial sensors typically include a magnetometer—a 3D compass that detects the local magnetic field to determine yaw direction. While intended to align with magnetic north, these sensors are highly susceptible to interference. Metal structures, power tools, and motors—commonly found on construction sites—can distort the Earth’s magnetic field, leading to inaccurate readings. To overcome this issue, SciTrack has developed a magnetometer-free inertial BSN approach which uses motion-based intrinsic alignment for precise tracking. The system has been executed on-body using a Xenoma e-skin suit. The suit features very flat IMUs placed onto a tight full body suit which can comfortably be worn below protective clothing.

The development of the exoskeleton has been led by TecNALIA. At the core of this exoskeleton lies its advanced controller, designed to anticipate user intent based on the kinematic information provided by the BSN. It remains passive when assistance is unnecessary and activates precisely when support is required. To achieve this, the system employs a long short-term memory (LSTM) neural network, which is fed by the wearer’s joint angles. LSTMs are

Image above e-skin suit and exoskeleton integration

particularly well-suited for this task due to their ability to process sequential data, retain contextual information, adapt to varying sampling rates, and perform reliably across different users, making them an optimal choice for human intent recognition based on kinematic data.

The exoskeleton has been tested in both controlled real-world and laboratory environments in collaboration with Acciona. Bricklaying was selected as the use case due to its repetitive nature, which demands frequent adjustments in the exoskeleton’s state. In this scenario, workers benefited from the exoskeleton’s automatic activation and deactivation feature. The task was performed under three different conditions: without an exoskeleton, with a passive exoskeleton, and using Humantech active exoskeleton. Users found the exoskeleton technology particularly valuable for the task, expressing a preference for the Humantech exoskeleton due to its seamless automatic functionality.

Image above HT exoskeleton in laboratory environment **left** and controlled real-world environment **middle**, commercial exoskeleton in real-world controlled environment **right**

BIMSpace XR Solution

Partners involved

HOLOLIGHT, CATENDA, ZHAW, IMPLENIA

Reference deliverables and useful material

D4.4 BIMxD XR visualization prototype (HOLO)

D6.5 Workflow capturing scientific report (DFKI)

D7.1 Pilot I - Dynamic semantic digital twin (IMPL)

Description of the technology

The BIMSpace XR solution is a mixed-reality application that enables real-time, true-to-scale visualization of high-quality BIM models directly on construction sites. Using industry-standard markers, the app ensures precise alignment between digital models and physical structures.

The XR app supports real-time issue tracking via BIM Collaboration Format (BCF), allowing users to annotate, analyze, and resolve design deviations, construction errors, or safety hazards on-site. These BCF issues sync in re-

al-time with BIM collaboration platforms like Catenda Hub, ensuring seamless project coordination.

Additionally, the app facilitates progress tracking by comparing as-planned vs. as-built conditions, identifying discrepancies, and enabling informed decision-making. It is also highly adaptable, supporting MEP review, VR environments, safety training, and multi-user sessions for interactive, scenario-based learning. As part of HumanTech Pilot 1, the BIMSpace XR app will allow users to interact with complex 3D IFC models, review and annotate them, and perform hazard detection and progress monitoring, improving accuracy and decision-making on-site.

What does BIMSpace XR solution do?

- Visualise BIM Models (.ifc)
- Marker-based alignment
- Read & Update BCF files from Catenda Hub
- Annotation features for review
- Voice-driven user interaction

Benefits for stakeholders /impact of the technology

The BIMSpace XR app transforms how stakeholders engage with construction projects by enhancing visualization, collaboration, and efficiency.

For Construction Teams & Site Workers

- Improved Accuracy and Spatial Understanding: True-to-scale BIM models overlaid onto real-world environments improves spatial understanding of the BIM models and reduces errors and rework.
- Real-Time Issue Resolution: BCF-based issue tracking ensures quick identification and resolution of design deviations, construction errors, and hazards.
- Enhanced Safety: Hazard visualization and safety training in XR reduce on-site risks.

For Project Managers & Coordinators

- Better Progress Tracking: Side-by-side comparisons of as-planned vs. as-built conditions enable proactive decision-making.
- Seamless Coordination: Integration with BIM collaboration platforms like Catenda Hub ensures synchronized data across teams.
- Reduced Delays & Costs: Early detection of issues prevents expensive rework and project delays.

For Architects & Engineers

- Enhanced Design Review: Interactive 3D models in XR allow detailed inspection, improving design validation and constructability assessments.
- Remote Collaboration: Multi-user XR sessions enable experts to provide input from different locations, streamlining workflows.

For Owners & Clients

- Greater Project Transparency: Clients can visualize construction progress and design intent in immersive detail.
- Informed Decision-Making: Access to real-time construction insights ensures that investments align with project goals.

For Training & Workforce Development

- Interactive Learning: XR enables hands-on, scenario-based training for workers in a safe and controlled environment.
- Skill Development: Reduces the learning curve for new workers by providing intuitive, real-world BIM interaction.

Object Pose Estimation for robotic grasping

Partners involved

DFKI

Reference deliverables and useful material

D5.4 Scientific report on unseen object class and shape estimation for robotic grasping

D7.2 Pilot II - Human-Robot collaboration and wearables

Description of the technology

A fundamental requirement in many robotic tasks—such as object grasping, assembly, and manipulation—is the accurate estimation of an object’s six-degree-of-freedom (6-DoF) pose (i.e., their exact location and orientation in 3D space). Reliable object pose information enables robots to make informed decisions about how to approach, grasp, and manipulate objects in their workspace. This is especially critical in industrial automation, where high precision and repeatability are mandatory.

A key challenge in robotic perception lies in obtaining accurate pose esti-

mates under real-world conditions, including variations in lighting, occlusion, and sensor noise. One effective approach to addressing this challenge involves training deep learning-based pose estimation models on synthetic data generated from CAD models.

This synthetic-to-real training paradigm offers significant advantages, such as eliminating the need for labour-intensive manual annotations and enabling large-scale dataset generation across diverse object categories. Despite domain gaps between synthetic and real data, recent advancements in domain adaptation and photorealistic rendering have made this approach increasingly viable for deployment in real-world robotic systems.

In our work at DFKI, we address this challenge within the context of robotic brick picking. For the robot to execute grasping actions successfully, it must have knowledge of two critical elements: 1) the poses of the bricks, and 2) the selection of an appropriate brick from a stack. To enable this, we developed a state-of-the-art, in-house deep learning-based pose estimation algorithm capable of predicting object poses directly from a single RGB image. This vision-based system allows the robot to perceive and localize the bricks in real time using only visual input.

Our research efforts and the algorithms developed within the project have received significant international recognition. They resulted in a publication at the prestigious CVPR2024 conference and a journal paper in IEEE TIP (Transactions on Image Processing). In addition, our work was awarded multiple prizes at the BOP (Benchmark for Object Pose) Challenge in both 2022 and 2023.

Given the novelty of the task and the lack of publicly available datasets for brick pose estimation, we generated a synthetic dataset using CAD model of bricks. The synthetic images are rendered with realistic variations in light-

ing, occlusion, and viewpoint to simulate real-world brick stacking scenarios. This approach enables scalable training of our neural network without the need for time-consuming and error-prone manual annotation. The resulting network demonstrates strong generalization to real-world scenes, enabling accurate and robust pose retrieval.

In addition to pose estimation, we developed a best-candidate selection algorithm that evaluates the predicted poses from the entire brick stack and identifies the most suitable brick for the robot to grasp. The selection criteria consider factors such as accessibility, orientation, and the physical feasibility of the grasp.

Benefits for stakeholders /impact of the technology

We then integrated different components of the pose estimation and selection into a complete end-to-end pipeline featuring an API interface for easy deployment.

The system operates in real time and is optimized for execution on edge devices such as the NVIDIA Jetson, making it well-suited for embedded robotic platforms in industrial environments.

The pipeline was then deployed and integrated with the Robotic platform provided by Baubot. This was done at multiple collaboration hackathons and meetings (both in person and online) with our partner SINTEF. The best brick candidate information provided by the API is used by SINTEF to trigger the robotic arm to approach and grasp the best suitable brick. We demonstrated the effectiveness of the technologies in the Pilot 2.

Although, in the scope of the HumanTech project we demonstrated the algorithm for pose estimation and selection for a brick, our pipeline can be utilized for any other novel object as well.

Glove for Human-Robot Interaction

Partners involved

SINTEF, BAuA, ACCIONA

Reference deliverables and useful material

D5.6 Communication framework for control and supervision

Description of the technology

The developed technology utilizes glove tracking for direct robot control in a situation when human and robot interact for completing a common task. Glove tracking prototype comprises of two main parts: a workshop glove with the attached small LEDs in a specific pattern and a robot-mounted tool with a stereo-vision camera system.

Glove utilizes so-called visual servoing, which is implemented as a real-time feedback control using computer vision. Stereo vision cameras can detect LED patterns and the system defines the robot control signal such that the robot tool can follow the glove motion.

This way a human can move the robot tool to another giving more flexibility for collaborative tasks. In addition, no specific knowledge in robot programming is required. Glove tracking is activated by showing a specific sequence of hand gestures.

Benefits for stakeholders /impact of the technology

The glove tracking technology was tested in the lab environment for the collaborative bricklaying process. The robot supported a human bricklayer by picking up bricks and handing-over to the exact location where the brick had to be laid. The bricklayer could use glove tracking to adjust the brick delivery position, for example for starting a new row. In addition, the delivery height could be adjusted for better ergonomics.

Utilisation of robotic technology with simplified robot control (such as glove tracking) can significantly improve working conditions by taking over repetitive and physically demanding tasks. Although glove tracking was tested for a bricklaying process, there is potential for applications in the other construction processes where a skilled worker could benefit from human-robot interaction and collaboration.

Learning by demonstration for mastic application

Partners involved

TECNALIA, ACCIONA, SINTEF, BAuA

Reference deliverables and useful material

D5.5 Scientific report on teaching control policies by teleoperation

D7.5 Pilot V - Robotic mastic application

Description of the technology

The HumanTech project is dedicated to creating human-centered technological advancements that boost safety, efficiency, and sustainability in the European construction industry. The learning from demonstration approach has examined the feasibility and advantages of utilizing robotic technology for applying mastic to concrete expansion joints, as an alternative to traditional manual methods.

Traditional manual process of sealing expansion joints is crucial for preventing water infiltration and maintaining structural integrity. For years, the

construction industry has grappled with the arduous and hazardous task of manually applying mastic to joints. This process requires workers to exert considerable physical effort, often in uncomfortable and unnatural positions, which can lead to work-related musculoskeletal injuries. Prolonged exposure to such conditions can cause chronic pain and discomfort, significantly impacting the well-being of construction workers. Moreover, the close proximity of workers to hazardous zones heightens the risk of accidents, further jeopardizing their safety.

In a bid to mitigate the risks and enhance the occupational well-being of construction workers, we have proposed an automated system for mastic application. By leveraging robotics, we can effectively alleviate the physical toll and hazards associated with manual mastic filling. The robotic solution assumes the responsibility of applying mastic, thereby maintaining a safe distance between workers and the hazardous working zone, significantly reducing the likelihood of accidents. By automating this process, we have created a safer, healthier, and more sustainable work environment, empowering construction workers to focus on more complex and high-value tasks that demand their skills and expertise.

The proposed solution is a human – robot collaboration strategy, being the human, the teacher in the process. We have adopted this solution due to the temperature-dependent properties of mastic. This poses a major challenge in industrial automation, as traditional programming approaches may not be effective across varying temperature conditions (they rely on fixed rigid control logic, so the robot program that works in the warm temperatures of August may not work in the colder temperatures of December).

To overcome this limitation, we utilize learning from human demonstrations (LfD) techniques, which allow the system to learn from human operators and adapt to changing environmental conditions. The human demonstration is

performed via teleoperation which ensures a safe distance from the mastic application zone. Our approach requires minimal training data, reducing the need for extensive retraining and minimizing the mental burden on human operators. This enables the system to rapidly adjust to temperature and environmental fluctuations, ensuring optimal performance across a range of conditions as it relays on the human demonstration made instants before. By integrating LfD with efficient training capabilities, we have developed a robust and adaptive system that can effectively handle the dynamic properties of the mastic.

The pilot successfully showcased the potential of robotic mastic application in construction, offering significant improvements in safety and efficiency. Future developments will focus on the aspects that would make the system fully functional for a construction site.

The pilot results are currently being evaluated for potential publication in a journal.

Micro Learning Units

Partners involved

TUS, EBC, DFKI

Reference deliverables and useful material

D7.1 HT micro-learning unit (MLU) descriptors

D6.2 Training monitoring and evaluation report

All the HT Training Microlearning units material has been made available open access on the Zenodo platform where they can be downloaded.

These modules can be seen using the following links:

Module 1: HumanTech Training material - HumanTech and Digitalisation

Module 2: HumanTech Training material - Green Technology in Construction

Module 3: HumanTech Training material - BIM Fundamentals

Module 4: HumanTech Training material - BIM Fundamentals On-Site

Module 5: HumanTech Training Material - BIM management

Module 6: HumanTech Training material - Digital Twin

Module 7: HumanTech Training material - UAV and UGV

Module 8: HumanTech Training material - Extended Reality and Exoskeletons

Module 9: HumanTech Training material - Robotics in Construction

Module 10: HumanTech Training material - Cameras and Mounting on Robotics, Drones, and Wearable

Description of the technology

A total of 10 micro-learning units (MLU) and the resulting learning outcomes have been developed, with a focus on technologies supporting workers' safety and well-being in future digital construction, human-robot collaboration in construction automation, sustainability within the construction sector and Health and Safety.

The development of these MLU's descriptors, content and the resulting learning outcomes have been the result of a collaborative process, and the HT partners and project results have heavily influenced the content of the resulting training material.

The MLUs content has been defined and created utilising:

1. Both industry and educational expertise within the HT project.
2. Existing e-learning platforms and freely available training materials which has been integrated into the learning units. This freely available training material derived from other European Funded projects such as Construction Blueprint and BIMzeED3 (and fully credited) has been edited and updated following consultation with HT project partners.
3. The work carried out in the HT project is sourced mainly from the HT project outputs. This has driven by the findings presented in the HT deliverables and work packages, papers created as outputs by HT partners and pilot site results.

Benefits for stakeholders /impact of the technology

The MLU and training material are an Open Educational Resources (OER) which will allow to be utilised throughout Europe.

The learning units and training materials have been created focusing on the trainers and the learners.

Training has been designed to be carried out with in higher education (HE), vocational education and training (VET) or in industry.

The materials created are adaptable and easily integrated into existing training to further enhance the training already being provided through continued professional development (CPD). TUS has structured the training resources using common MUs enabling flexible blended and on-site delivery. Trainers will be able to deliver more flexible and innovative ways of upskilling.

The training has been developed to be delivered utilising a flexible delivery method, meaning the material must be usable in a variety of modalities such as in class, on-line, on-site, in-house and/or blended. This is due to the training being suitable for delivery to HEI, VET and to industry learners.

Automatic Bridge Defect Detection

Partners involved

RPTU, ZHAW, STRUCINSPECT

Reference deliverables and useful material

D7.4 Pilot IV - Bridge inspection and monitoring

Description of the technology

Drone-Based Data Capturing of Bridges

Drones equipped with high-resolution cameras capture detailed images of bridges, including hard-to-reach areas. It's important to capture everything from the bridge to ensure comprehensive inspection.

Photogrammetric Processing of Images

Photogrammetry processes these images to create accurate 3D models by stitching together overlapping images.

Automated AI Defect Detection

AI algorithms analyze the images to identify defects such as cracks, spalling, exposed reinforcement, corrosion, and efflorescence.

Mapping Detected Defects on the 3D Model

STRUCINSPECT's method involves transforming 2D damage information from images onto the 3D model. This approach enhances spatial awareness and orientation during damage evaluation, allowing for precise localization and visualization of defects on the textured 3D model.

Generating IFCs and BIM Model

Industry Foundation Classes (IFCs) are automatically generated from this data, resulting in a Building Information Modeling (BIM) model.

Benefits for stakeholders /impact of the technology

- **Enhanced Accuracy:** Precise defect mapping improves the accuracy of inspections and maintenance planning.
- **Improved Visualization:** 3D models with mapped defects provide a clear visual representation, aiding in better understanding and prioritization of repairs.
- **Efficient Monitoring:** Continuous updates to the 3D model with new defect data ensure ongoing assessment of the bridge's condition.
- **Collaboration:** BIM models facilitate better collaboration among stakeholders, ensuring all parties have access to detailed and accurate information.

BIMxD-based robot navigation

Partners involved

RPTU, BAUBOT, TECHNALIA, STAM, CATENDA, RICOH, SINTEF, KAJIMA

Reference deliverables and useful material

D7.3 Pilot III - Remote controlled demolition

Description of the technology

The research aimed to show how the building information saved in BIM models can be used to perform typical robotic tasks like localization and navigation. The BIM software Catenda Hub is used to remotely select marking positions for the robot. Next, a task planner assigned these positions and forwarded them to the robotic platform Pluto.

First, the robot localizes itself within the building. The localization is based on a BIM model of the building the robot is operating in and on point clouds created by a 360° lidar scanner. For the localization, two steps had to be performed. First, the robot's current room is identified.

Then, the precise position within the room is detected. For the localization, geometric features of the BIM model are detected, and a 2D map of the environment is created. Each room's detected features are mapped to the features detected by the measured point cloud.

By that, the current room is identified. For precise localization, the distance of the features in the room model and the point cloud are used to triangulate the position. Since this method is not stable in all situations, e.g., while driving through a door, the odometry of the vehicle is also considered in the localization. The image below shows a scan and the detected features (colored boxes).

An elastic band fusion algorithm is used for navigation. A grid map of the building is created from the BIM file. Rough target points for the navigation are calculated using a flood fill algorithm. These points are used as initial points for the elastic band fusion algorithm. Based on the distance to the closest obstacle, the points are adjusted. The robot always targets the next target point on the list until the destination is reached. The grid map and a snapshot of the navigation algorithm are shown in the images below.

The approach shows how the information from BIM models can be used for typical robotic tasks such as localization and navigation. The experiments conceptually showed how this information can be utilized to perform construction tasks.

After reaching the target position, the robotic arm marks positions on the wall. Therefore, a marking tool is used to detect the contact to the wall. The images below show the robot driving through the experiment environment and the robotic arm during the marking task.

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